

Survey of insects and diseases in Asia

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In a 1975 IRRI survey, 35 rice breeders at 28 research centers in 10 Asian nations were asked to rank, in order of severity, the four most serious insects and diseases that limit farmers' rice yields within the area served by each experiment station. The project was conducted in collaboration with Iowa State University, USA, and was partially funded by The Rockefeller Foundation.

The rice stem borer was most widely considered a serious pest. In 60% of 35 regions, its severity rating was 1.6, one of the highest, on a scale where 1 = most serious pest and 4 = fourth most serious. But when severity rating was calculated only for the stations where the stem borer was one of the four most serious problems, it rated fourth highest, 2.7 (see table). That may indicate that although the stem borer limits yields across vast regions, other local pests are usually more serious in individual areas.

Bacterial blight disease, with an overall severity rating of 1.6, was considered a major problem in 57% of the regions. Where bacterial blight was serious, it

Rice breeders' perceptions of the specific insect and disease pests that most seriously limit rice production in farmers' fields within the areas served by their research centers. Thirty-five rice breeders at 28 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations, 1975.

Pest	Mean severity rating ^a		Breeders (%) who rated pest as one of 4 major constraints
	All stations	Stations where pest is a problem	
Stem borer	1.6	2.7	60
Bacterial blight	1.6	2.8	57
Brown planthopper	1.1	2.5	46
Blast disease	1.4	3.2	43
Gall midge	1.1	3.0	37
Tungro virus	0.7	2.3	29
Sheath blight	0.3	2.0	17
Green leafhopper	0.2	2.0	9
Helminthosporium	0.1	1.3	9
Striped virus ^b	0.3	3.0	9
Grassy stunt virus	0.1	1.0	6
Sheath rot	0.1	2.0	6
Other insects ^c	0.7	2.1	34
Other diseases ^d	0.4	2.1	20

^aOn a scale of 1-4: 4 = most serious insect or disease pest; 1 = fourth most serious. Calculated for all 35 areas and for only those regions in which each factor was considered one of four major pests.

^bOnly in Korea.

^cIncludes one rating each for whitebacked planthopper, leaf roller, paddy bug, seedling fly, stink bug, armyworm, gandhi bug, and two unspecified insects.

^dIncludes one rating each for bacterial leaf streak, black smut, sheath virus, glume blotch, stem rot, and two unspecified diseases.

received a rating of 2.8 — higher than that for the stem borer. The brown planthopper was a major pest in 46% of the regions. Its overall severity rating was 1.1 ; but in regions where it was a problem, it was rated 2.5. The fourth

most common of the serious Pests was blast disease, cited in 43% of the regions. It received an overall severity rating of 1.4, but at stations where it was a major problem, it had the highest rating, 3.2.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

IR26 found susceptible to the brown planthopper in North Sumatra, Indonesia

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The brown planthopper (BPH) has severely attacked rice in North Sumatra since about 1970. IR26 was first grown from 5 kg of seed brought to N. Sumatra from IRRI in 1974. Seedlings were transplanted near Tebingtinggi on 15 May 1974 and 3 t were harvested. By the end of March 1975 (the following season), IR26 was grown on about 67 ha; about 200 t were harvested. IR26 was planted on about 860 ha in the 1975–76wet

Empty areas where IR34 was hopperburned during early growth stages.

season and on about 30,600 ha in the 1976–77 wet season.

IR26 was first reported to be damaged by the BPH in September 1976. In February 1977 hopperburn was confirmed in IR26 and IR34, and IR30 was severely attacked (see photo). At three locations, IR32 appeared resistant; at one location, IR36 seemed resistant. The highest BPH populations (adults + nymphs/hill) were 1,008 on IR26, 1,508 on IR30, 47 on IR32, 18 on IR34, and 40 on IR36. Most of the insects were in the first and second instars, except for two cases of more advanced insect development on IR26. No hill in 11 fields was found infected with symptoms of grassy stunt; 24% infection was observed in 1 field. On December 15, 1976, the Extension Service of the N. Sumatra provincial government estimated the total area of rice fields attacked as 43,618 ha, with 3,482 ha of hopperburn. On 31 January 1977, 43,783 ha of BPH damage was reported, with 7,597 ha of hopperburn. About 9,400 ha of the damage and 880 ha of the hopperburn were on IR26. This was the first report of large areas of IR26 being severely attacked by the BPH in Indonesia. ❧

Population fluctuation of brown planthopper in Kuttanadu, Kerala, India

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The brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* is a major rice pest in Kerala. Its first reported outbreak was in the punja crop of 1973–74. It caused extensive damage in Kuttanadu, Alleppey district, and in the Kole areas of Trichur district.

These rice-growing tracts are waterlogged and the fields must be drained after the monsoon rains for paddy cultivation. Rice is extensively grown, mostly as a monoculture crop. After one or two rice crops, the fields remain under water for the rest of the year. Notable features of rice cultivation in these areas that may favor the BPH are widespread cultivation of susceptible high yielding varieties, such as Jaya and IR8; high

seeding rates; excessive nitrogen use; indiscriminate insecticide application, which causes destruction of natural enemies; and favorable climatic factors.

The Rice Research Station, Moncompu, concentrates its efforts on the BPH problem through a multidisciplinary approach. To study the population fluctuations, we have recorded light-trap catches of BPH in Kuttanadu since January 1974.

The population peaks twice each year, in each cropping season. The maximum catch was recorded from January to March, with the highest peak in February. Interestingly, this peak coincides with the booting and postflowering stages of the main crop (Oct.–Nov. to Feb.–Mar.). Hopperburn and serious crop losses are common during this period. The BPH population begins to decline by late March when the harvest ends and continues to drop until July. The next peak is from July to September, during the autumn crop. But because of adverse climatic conditions, such as heavy rains and high winds, the population does not rise to alarming proportions during this period, and so the crop is safe. The light-trap studies also show that BPH are present throughout the year. Survival of the pest during the off-season, when there is no standing crop, should be further investigated. ❧

Varietal resistance to the rice thrip, *Baliothrips biformis*

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Baliothrips biformis is primarily a pest of seedling paddy which emerges in the drier months and infests the late-planted crops in both crop seasons in Sri Lanka. Depending on the degree of infestation, the insect can retard growth or kill the seedling. Breeding for thrip resistance would be the most economical means of control. Of the almost 800 indigenous varieties that underwent preliminary observation, those that showed reasonably good levels of resistance were field-tested in replicated trials

during the 1976 and 1977 dry seasons. Damage was observed at 2 weeks after seeding or at the 3- to 4-leaf stage. The system of evaluation was as follows.

Reaction ¹	Damage
R	Leaves remained healthy except for very slight rolling of the first and second leaf.
MR	Slight rolling and withering of the first and second leaf.
MS	First and second leaf withered and dead; upper leaves slightly rolled.
S	Upper leaves rolled, withered, and with few white lesions; lower leaves dead.
HS	Upper leaves dying with pronounced white lesions, seedlings are stunted; lower leaves dead.

¹R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

Varieties found resistant and moderately resistant to the pest are listed below.

Variety	Reaction
Dahanala 2220	R
Dahanala 682	R
Kaluheenati 547	R/MR
Heenati 896	MR
Mudukiriyal 197	MR
Kalubalawee	MR
Demalakotan 1630	MR
Gonabaru	MR/MS

Serious attacks of rice gall midge in the central plain of Thailand

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The rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* has long been one of the most important rice pests in northern and northeastern Thailand, but not in the central rice-growing area. In June 1977, however,